
CSCCE Tech Case Study: Using Read the Docs to collaboratively create documentation in GitHub for Zarr

About this case study

In 2023, CSCCE hosted a series of community “Tools Trials” that focused on tools commonly used for community management in open-source and open-source-supporting communities. The goal of the series - which consisted of several live webinars with Q&A and this accompanying tip sheet collection - was to share existing knowledge and provide any scientific community manager with options about tools and use cases they could explore further.

One of the most commonly used tools by these communities is GitHub. In this case study, we summarize how the Zarr community uses GitHub and Read the Docs to create documentation.

What is GitHub?

[GitHub](#) is a version control platform for storing, collaborating on, and tracking projects. It is primarily used for software development, but can also be used for other collaborative work. It utilizes [Git](#), which is an open-source version control system that can track which users make changes to computer files (e.g., code, documents) and when. Although there are other software platforms that use Git, GitHub is the most popular. [Check out our introductory tip sheet for more information.](#)

Overview of Zarr

[Zarr](#) is an open-source data format for the storage of large N-dimensional typed arrays (aka tensors) in chunked and compressed manner. Zarr was authored by Alistair Miles and is currently developed and maintained by volunteer contributors. Community members connect every two weeks at community and ZEP (Zarr Enhancement Proposal) meetings. You can find out more about joining Zarr Community events by [viewing the calendar](#).

What is Read the Docs?

[Read the Docs](#) simplifies software documentation by building, versioning, and hosting your documents, automatically. It’s a free, open-source tool that hosts more than 80000 projects and has over 100000 users. Treating documentation like code allows GitHub-savvy community members to use the tools they already use to contribute to the upkeep of community documentation. Read the Docs can host multiple versions of your docs, pulled directly from Git. Read the Docs has a [template repository](#) hosted on GitHub. This repository contains all the necessary files to create, build, and host an online documentation hub.

Read the Docs is [free for OS communities](#), however they do [offer paid plans](#) that add additional features, such as private repository support and single sign-on.

Getting set up with Read the Docs

To use Read the Docs to create documentation for your organization on GitHub, start by using the [Read the Docs template to create a new repo](#). Click on 'Use this template' and then choose "create a new repository" (Figure 1).

Figure 1
Screenshot of Read the Docs template tutorial available on GitHub.

Once you have chosen to create a new repository, you will need to add a name for your new repository to associate it with your project and then click on the "Create repository" button found at the bottom of the form. This new repo has all the files you need to build your online documentation.

To actually build your documentation, you'll need to [sign up for a Read the Docs account](#), which you can connect to your GitHub account. From there, you can give Read the Docs access to your repo, and [ask it to build your documentation](#). This automatic process takes approximately 2-3 minutes and will display on the "Builds" tab within your dashboard and will also be available in the docs folder of your GitHub repository. Within GitHub, you can utilize features like assigning reviewers to the documentation. Figure 2 provides an example of documentation rendered using Read the Docs for the CSCCE open-source tools trials.

Figure 2

An example of documentation generated by Read the Docs.

Pros and cons of using GitHub for this use case

[For general pros and cons of using GitHub for community management, [please refer to our overview tip sheet.](#)]

Pros:

- GitHub integrates seamlessly with Read the Docs, making it easy for users to collaborate and contribute to documentation.
- Read the Docs is also an open-source tool.

Cons:

- Some setup is required, and depending on your needs, this solution may not be free (e.g., if you're repository is private).

Additional resources

- [Sanket Verma's full presentation on integrating Read the Docs with GitHub](#) - Watch this case study being presented during CSCCE's Tools Trial in this short video
- [Zarr Specification documentation](#)
- Learn more about Read the Docs' features - <https://about.readthedocs.com/features/>

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Citing and reusing this tip sheet

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